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Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cold Cream for Psoriasis

Vishakha Borkar*, Namrata Chavan, Arpita Chopade, Pradnya Chavan, Trupti Harne

Dnyansadhana college of pharmacy, Parbhani.

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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic, inflammatory skin disorder characterized by accelerated epidermal turnover, leading to the formation of plaques and scaling. The present research work includes topical treatment, including topical herbal cold cream with their rich bioactive compounds, have been explored as potential treatment for psoriasis due to their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immune-modulatory properties. Herbal cold cream includes extract of plant such as Azadirachta Indica, Cocos Nucifera Oil, Bitter Almond Oil, Ricinus Oil, have shown effective in alleviating psoriasis symptoms, reducing skin lesion, and improving overall skin health. While herbal cold cream often fewer side effects compared to conventional therapies, their efficacy and safety require further validation through well-designed clinical trials. The extract of herbal drugs plays effective role in the treatment of psoriasis, mechanisms of action. Psoriasis: Chronic inflammatory skin disease characterized by Red, scaly patches and Irritation The present study focuses on natural herbal ingredients with their properties used to prepare herbal cold cream to help relieve the symptoms of psoriasis. Herbal ingredients: Neem, bees wax, Coconut oil, Almond oil, etc. Benefits: Fewer side effects, symptom relief, improved skin health.

INTRODUCTION

Around 80% of the world's population receives primary from herbal remedies mostly in developing nations. They have endured over time because of their safety, effectiveness, cultural acceptability and lack of adverse consequences. In addition, herbal remedies for age – related

illness Such as memory loss, osteoporosis, osteoarthritis, diabetes, immune system, liver and other ailments are motioned in ancient literature. For these conditions, palliative care is the only treatment available. Since their chemical components are involved in the physiological processes of live plants, they are thought to be more suited to human health. More than 1.5

***Corresponding Author:** Vishakha Borkar

Address: Dnyansadhana college of pharmacy, Parbhani..

Email ✉: vish.borkar92@gmail.com

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million people use medicinal herbs for therapeutic, promoting and preventive purpose as part of a traditional medical system. Plant are prospective sources of herbal formulations, and their use has drawn interest from experts in a variety of medical specialties as well as scientific communities from other fields. The number of companies producing herbal treatment has increased as a result of the growing use of this drug due to the toxicity and adverse effects of allopathic medicines. The number of non-prescription users of herbal drugs has increased during the last few decades. These medications have held up well to thousands of years of humans testing and real-world testing. Some medicines have been withdrawn because they are too toxic, while others have had their side effect adjusted or balanced by adding more herbs. Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune skin condition where the immune system speeds up the growth of skin cells, causing dry, scaly, and itchy patches. Natural ingredients like neem, coconut oil, and almond oil are gaining popularity for their anti-inflammatory and healing properties. Herbal cold creams made with these ingredients help restore the skin barrier, lock in moisture, and reduce irritation making them safe and effective for sensitive skin.

- 1) **Plaque psoriasis:** The most common type of psoriasis causes dry, itchy raised skin patches covered with scalp. There may be few or many. They usually appear on the elbows, knees, lower back and scalp. The patches vary in colour, depending on skin colour.
- 2) **Nail psoriasis:** Psoriasis can affect fingernails and toenails, causing pitting, abnormal nail growth and discoloration. Psoriatic nails might loosen and separate from the nail bed. Several diseases may cause the nail to crumble.
- 3) **Guttate psoriasis:** Guttate psoriasis primarily affects young adults and children. It's usually triggered by bacterial infection such as strep throat. It's marked by small, drop-shaped, scaling spots on the trunk, arms or legs.
- 4) **Inverse psoriasis:** Inverse psoriasis mainly affects the skin folds of the groin, buttock and breasts. It causes smooth patches of inflamed skin that worsen with friction and sweating fungal infection may trigger that type of psoriasis.
- 5) **Pustular psoriasis:** Pustular psoriasis, a rare type, cause clearly defined pus-filled blisters. It can occur in widespread patches or on small areas of the palms or soles.

Different type of psoriasis:

Fig No:1. Plaque psoriasis.

Fig No:2. Nail psoriasis.

Fig No:3. Guttate psoriasis

Fig No:4. Inverse psoriasis.

Fig No:5. Pustular Psoriasis.

Herbs used for preparation

Sr.No	Herb used	Chemical constituent	Activity	Uses	Image
1	Neem:	Azadirachtin, Nimbi, Nimbidin, Gedunin Fatty acids	Antibacterial, Antifungal, Antiviral, Antiseptic, Anti-inflammatory	Leaves.	
2.	Coconut Oil:	Medium-chain fatty acid	Antibacterial and antifungal.	Cosmetic and skincare.	
3.	Almond Oil	Fatty acid and Vitamins.	Emollient, Anti-inflammatory and moisturizing	Pharmaceuticals and hair care.	
4	Castor Oil:	Ricinoleic acid	Anti-inflammatory and Antimicrobial	Industrial and cosmetic.	
5	Rosemar y Oil:	Camphor, Limonene and Alpha-pinene.	Camphor, Limonene and Alpha-pinene.	Aromatherapy and cosmetic.	

6	Vitamin E capsules	Fatty acid, Gelatin, Glycerine.	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory	deficiencies, protect cells from oxidative stress, and support skin, hair, and immune health.	
7	Rose Water:	Linalool.	hydrating, soothing, and balancing properties	skincare as a natural facial toner or hydrating mist.	

INGREDIENTS

Sr. no	Ingredients	Quantity	Use
1.	Bees wax	12g	Skin softeing
2.	Coconut Oil	10ml	Texture and effectiveness
3.	Sweet Almond Oil	15ml	Nourishing
4.	Castor Oil	05ml	To reduce redness and inflammation
5.	Neem Oil	10ml	To reduce itchiness and pain
6.	Vitamin E Capsule	2	Antioxidant
7.	Rose Water	10 drops	soothing
8.	Rosemary Oil	15 drops	Fragrance
9	Emulsifying agent(Borax) Sodium borate	0.5g	Stability

Formulation of Cold Cream:

- Firstly, take coconut oil, Bees Wax , sweet almond oil, and castor oil. Add them into a clean beaker.
- Place the beaker on a heating mantle. Heat gently until all ingredient are fully melted and mixed
- After the oils are melted, remove from heat. Add neem oil and squeeze in the vitamin E capsules. Mix well.Place the beaker in the freezer for about 10 minutes.
- Wait until the mixture becomes slightly opaque. It should look cloudy but still be a little runny.
- Take the beaker out of the freezer.
- Add 5 drops of rosemary oil, and 4-5.

Dissolve borax complently in hot water at the same temperature.

- Add the hot water phase into hot oil phase & stir continuously.
- Mix everything thoroughly until the cream has a smooth, cold-cream-like texture.
- Store the cold cream in a clean container. keep in a cool, dry place

Final Product

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Kamlesh Kumar Singh et.al (2014): Psoriasis is an immune-mediated disease with no permanent

cure, and while treatments exist, some can worsen the condition. Herbal drug, due to their safety and availability, show promise as effective anti-psoriatic agent, requiring and understanding of key mechanisms like T-cell activation and cytokine inhibition for development.

Ravindra Ganpati Gaikwad et.al (2022): Psoriasis causes red, scaly patches and can be treated with systemic, topical, or phototherapy, though these options have significant side effect. Herbal medicines offer promising, safe and affordable alternative, and this study highlights plants and formulation that could lead to better treatments.

Anna Herman et.al (2016): This formulation covers the mechanisms of herbal product in psoriasis, including inhibiting keratinocyte hyperproliferation, immune-inflammatory reaction, PHK activity, and the hedgehog signalling pathway.

Jayakar Thomas et.al (2019): Psoriasis is estimated to affect 0.44-2.8% of the Indian population. Moisturizers are a key adjuvant psoriasis treatment strategy, but data regarding their effectiveness, safety and compliance in an Indian context are lacking.

Tejpal Yadav et.al (2024): Psoriasis is a chronic condition that can strike at any age. This sickness is associated with inflammatory problems that impact all human in the world. Psoriasis is more common in Scandinavians than in Asian and African populations due to a combination of factors such as age, genetic, geographic location, factor. Immune stimulation, genetic contribution, antimicrobial peptides, and other significant triggers such as medicines, immunization, infections, trauma, stress, obesity, alcohol intake, smoking, air pollution, sun exposure, and particular disorders cause psoriasis.

Sakshi Kaneria et.al (2024): Psoriasis is an immune-mediated disease with an unclear cause marked by inflammation cause by dysfunction in

the immune system, which results in inflammation in various parts of the skin. It is mainly characterized by activation of T- cell, abnormal increase in keratinocyte, local vascular changes and stimulation of theneutrophil. There are lot of therapies used to treat Psoriasis including topical, systemic and phototherapy but none of them is able to cure the disease completely, inhibiting the long-term serious side effect for the human body.

N. Lathesh et.al (2024): The current study aims to prepare an herbal ointment using several extracts of the complete *Indigofera aspalathoides* plant and assess the extracts antimicrobial effectiveness for Psoriasis. The entire plant 's morphological and physiochemical characteristics were evaluated. Different extracts of powdered whole plant were made, and these extracts underwent phytochemical analysis.

CONCLUSION

Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with fewer side effects than the synthetic ones. So the herbal formulations with natural ingredients have growing demand in the world market. Natural ingredients like *Azadiracta indica*, coconut oil, sweet almond oil, castor oil are effective remedies in formulation of herbal cream for psoriasis. This natural ingredients in herbal cream can help alleviate symptoms such as dryness, scaling, and irritation without the harsh side effects often associated with synthetic treatment. As interest in natural skincare solutions continues to rise, herbal creams with these natural ingredients hold significant potential in the supportive care of psoriasis. Natural ingredients like *Azadiracta indica*, coconut oil, sweet almond oil, castor oil are effective remedies in formulation of herbal cream for psoriasis. This natural ingredients in herbal cream can help alleviate symptoms such as dryness, scaling, and irritation without the harsh side effects often associated with synthetic treatment. As interest in natural skincare

solutions continues to rise, herbal creams with these natural ingredients hold significant potential in the supportive care of psoriasis.

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14. Kamlesh Kumar Singh et al. (2014) – Discussed herbal drugs in psoriasis treatment, highlighting the role of T-cell activation and cytokine inhibition.
15. Ravindra Ganpati Gaikwad et al. (2022) – Described side effects of conventional psoriasis treatments and potential of herbal alternatives.
16. Anna Herman et al. (2016) – Explained mechanisms of herbal product action such as inhibition of keratinocyte hyperproliferation and modulation of immune response.
17. Jayakar Thomas et al. (2019) – Focused on moisturizers as adjuvant therapy in Indian psoriasis patients.
18. Tejpal Yadav et al. (2024) – Outlined factors triggering psoriasis, including genetics and environmental factors.
19. Sakshi Kaneria et al. (2024) – Described immune dysfunction as a core element in psoriasis and discussed limitations of current treatments.

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